

Q1 - "I agree to answer this survey, part of the European research project EcoBulk. It is clear to me that my answers are anonymous and I will not be asked to share any personal information"

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
"I agree to answer this survey, part of the European research project EcoBulk. It is clear to me that my answers are anonymous and I will not be asked to share any personal information"	1	1	1	0	0	9

Field	Choice Count
Yes	9
No	0
Total	9

Q4 - How aware or concerned are you of the following? (1 = Not aware nor concerned at all; 2 = Somewhat aware or concerned; 3 = Well aware or concerned)

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Waste management/disposal	2	3	3	0	0	9
Pollution by single use plastic	2	3	3	0	0	9
Recycling of plastics	1	3	3	1	0	9
Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)	1	3	3	1	0	9
Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	1	3	3	1	0	9
Reuse and repurposing of products	2	3	3	0	0	9

Field	1	2	3	Total
Waste management/disposal	0	1	8	9
Pollution by single use plastic	0	1	8	9
Recycling of plastics	1	0	8	9
Recycling of large bulky waste (e.g. from construction)	1	2	6	9
Recycling of composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	1	1	7	9

Reuse and repurposing of products

0 3 6 9

Q5 - For each of the following statements, select whether you Agree, Neither agree or disagree, or Disagree.

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
The UK as a whole generates too much waste	1	2	1	0	0	9
Your place of work generates too much waste	1	2	1	0	0	9
Your place of work makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	1	2	1	0	0	9
Your household generates too much waste	1	3	2	1	1	9
Your household makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	1	2	1	0	0	9

Field	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Total
The UK as a whole generates too much waste	8	1	0	9
Your place of work generates too much waste	5	4	0	9
Your place of work makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	5	4	0	9
Your household generates too much waste	4	2	3	9
Your household makes efforts to reduce the amount of waste and recycle more	8	1	0	9

Q6 - For these materials, select those that you think should have mainstream municipal recycling capabilities

Field	Choice Count
Steel	6
Aluminium	7
Glass	7
Soft plastic (plastics that can be crunched)	9
Composite materials (glass fibre, carbon fibre, others)	7
Hard plastic (plastics that can't be crunched)	9
Paper/wood/cardboard	9
Textiles	7
Other	0
Total	61

Other - Text

Q13 - When choosing between two different products, how likely is it that sustainability factors would affect your decision?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
When choosing between two different products, how likely is it that sustainability factors would affect your decision?	2	4	3	1	1	9

Field	Choice Count
Very likely	0
Likely	6
Equally likely	1
Unlikely	2
Very unlikely	0
No opinion	0
Total	9

Q8 - Does a product containing recycled material stop or deter you from buying, renting or leasing it?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Does a product containing recycled material stop or deter you from buying, renting or leasing it?	3	3	3	0	0	9

Field	Choice Count
Yes	0
Sometimes or maybe	0
No	9
No opinion	0
Total	9

Q9 - If yes, maybe or sometimes, why? (Several answers possible)

No data found - your filters may be too exclusive!

No data found - your filters may be too exclusive!

Other - Text

Q10 - Which product categories would you be likely to buy, rent or lease knowing that they contain recycled materials? (Select more than one if applicable)

Field	Choice Count
Clothing	8
Appliances and electronics	9
Games / toys	7
Vehicle parts / equipment	8
Sporting goods and equipment	8
Furniture (indoor and outdoor)	9
Other	0
Total	49

Other - Text

Q14 - How likely are you to buy:

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
A more costly, environmentally friendly product over a cheaper version	2	4	3	1	1	9
A product made from recycled materials over one with fully new/virgin material	2	3	2	0	0	9
A refurbished cheaper product over a fully new more expensive one	2	3	2	0	0	9

Field	Likely	Equally likely	Unlikely	No opinion	Total
A more costly, environmentally friendly product over a cheaper version	3	4	2	0	9
A product made from recycled materials over one with fully new/virgin material	5	4	0	0	9
A refurbished cheaper product over a fully new more expensive one	6	3	0	0	9

Q11 - Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick contains recycled materials make their "image" Better, Similar or Worse?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Does knowing that the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick contains recycled materials make their "image" Better, Similar or Worse?	1	2	1	0	0	9

Field	Choice Count
Better	8
Similar	1
Worse	0
No opinion	0
Total	9

Q12 - Did the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick affect your experience?

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	Responses
Did the material used for the construction of the shelter and furniture at the University of Warwick affect your experience?	1	4	3	1	1	9

Field	Choice Count
Yes	1
No	4
Somewhat	2
No opinion	2
Total	9

Q17 - Please let us know how the materials affected your experience

Please let us know how the materials affected your experience
